

Collision Avoidance Strategy for Autonomous Intersection Management by a Central Optimizer Algorithm

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Abstract—The increasing volume of traffic worldwide enlightens the problem of ensuring driving safety and preventing collisions at unsignalized intersections. In this regard, with the advent of Connected Autonomous Vehicles (CAV), Collision Avoidance (CA) and Autonomous Intersection Management (AIM) problems have been intensively studied and many cooperative and optimization-based approaches have been proposed. In this paper, we introduce a double-level collision-free control system, performed by a Central Optimizer (CO) and local CAV controllers, that allows CAVs to safely cross the intersection at the same time. The CO collects data from CAVs and imposes waiting times at specific waypoints that are then used by the low-level controllers to regulate the vehicle speed. The main advantage of the presented method is that a less complex optimization problem is formulated by imposing waiting times rather than determining the speed profile. A simulation campaign conducted on Matlab shows the performance of the proposed approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

After a fall due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of cars sold worldwide has been rising again since 2021. According to Scotiabank [1], by the end of 2023, 70.8 millions of vehicles will be sold in the global market. As a result, the increasing traffic volume emphasizes the problem of driving safety and road accidents.

Collision Avoidance (CA) technologies help to prevent collisions and mitigate driving safety problems. CA has been constantly studied over recent years. In [2], a recent survey of the state-of-the-art research in the field is provided that classifies available CA techniques in three different categories: (i) traditional methods, such as traffic rules and facilities, (ii) sensor-based methods, such as GPS, radar, ultrasonic and camera-vision systems and (iii) more recent solutions based on cooperation between vehicles and *Artificial Intelligence* (AI). While the first two categories depend, at least in part, on driver's response, the last one improves CA effectiveness accuracy and adaptability by leveraging on complex road management strategies that can be often combined with automatic control techniques of *Connected Autonomous Vehicles* (CAV).

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In most countries, car accidents occur more often on urban and rural roads rather than on highways [3]. More in detail, due mainly to human error, more than 40% of reported incidents occur at intersections [4]. Namazi *et al.* [5] argue that CAVs have the potential to improve traffic management efficiency at both signalized and unsignalized intersections. When it comes to Autonomous Intersection Management (AIM), they identify four major groups among the state-of-the-art methodologies: rule based, optimization-based, hybrid and machine learning. Moreover, they observe that most of the considered works have efficiency and safety as their primary objectives.

In [6], a set of safety-based rules to handle the crossing sequence of autonomous vehicles at unsignalized intersections is proposed. Each approaching vehicle takes its decision by exchanging data with other vehicles in a vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communication framework. A competitive computational market, where CAVs trade with a central system the use of intersection capacity, is suggested in [7]. The road traffic system is modeled as a distributed resource-allocation problem and market-based techniques as applied to handle crossing sequence.

A decentralized optimization-based solution is argued in [8]. CAVs have to coordinate among them to cross the intersection by solving local constrained optimization problems that minimize a cost function and prevent collisions. A more recent work [9] suggests a V2V-based decentralized approach that does not need a central coordinator and provides a consensus protocol to avoid collisions. The proposed approach minimizes delays or anticipations during the intersection crossing.

Alternatively, some works suggest the use of Model-Predictive-Control (MPC) both in centralized [10] and decentralized [11] fashion. A comparative study between different techniques in [12] shows that MPC had the best results compared to PID and Fuzzy Logic approaches due to its relatively low error margin and controller effort. In addition, other solutions propose Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) [13] and Integer Linear Programming (ILP) approaches [14] to solve the AIM problem.

Finally, when it comes to Deep Learning-based solutions, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) has been extensively used in recent years to solve autonomous driving tasks [15], [16] and specific approaches exist for the AIM problem [17].

In this paper, we focus on the AIM and CA problems in unsignalized intersections. In detail, we introduce a collision-

no collisions. The second level of the Control System is composed of the CAV local controllers, each one determines the vehicle speed profile to cross the intersection on the basis of the received waiting times at the waypoints.

The general scheme of the Control System is reported in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Control system scheme.

Let us suppose that there is a set of n AVs denoted by $N = \{1, \dots, i, \dots, n\}$ that have to cross the intersection. The following assumptions are imposed:

- $n \leq 4$ AVs are considered at the intersection with only one vehicle in each lane;
- each vehicle $i \in N$ forecasts to cross the intersection at a given constant speed v_0^i whether its motion is collision-free.

Before the vehicles enter the CZ, each AV local controller calculates the route to be performed in the intersection.

First, it is assumed that each AV i defines a set of subsequent way-points $\mathbf{p}^i = \{p_1^i, \dots, p_j^i, \dots, p_m^i\}$ with $p_j^i = (x_j^i, y_j^i)$ for each $j = 1, \dots, m$, where the coordinates x_j^i, y_j^i are defined with respect to a system of Cartesian axes with the origin positioned on the center of the intersection.

Second, the local controller of each AV i calculates the path as a continuous function $y = s^i(x)$ defined in the system of Cartesian axes by interpolating the way-points set \mathbf{p}^i using an Hermite spline. The Hermite formula is applied to each interval (p_j^i, p_{j+1}^i) separately. The resulting spline is a third degree polynomial and has a null continuous first derivative [18] at each way-point.

When each AV i enters the CZ and receives a signal from the CO, each local controller communicates to the CO the current AV position $(x^i(0), y^i(0))$, the speed $v^i(0)$, the way-points set \mathbf{p}^i and the planned path $y = s^i(x)$ in the form of a Hermite spline interpolating the way-points set \mathbf{p}^i . An example of AV paths sent to the CO is shown in Fig. 4.

III. INTERSECTION CONTROL SYSTEM

This section describes the actions and the strategy applied by the Control System when the AVs have to cross the intersection. When the CO receives the way-points, the current positions, the constant speeds and the paths by the AVs, it performs a centralized optimization having the objective

Fig. 4: Example of Cubic Hermite Spline

of avoiding collisions among vehicles and minimizing the waiting times.

We define the waiting time vector $\mathbf{w}^i = [w_1^i, \dots, w_j^i, \dots, w_m^i]^T$ for each $i \in V$ where each $w_j^i \geq 0$ represents a time that the AV i has to wait at the way-point p_j^i before proceeding again at constant speed. The waiting times are subsequently sent to the local AV controllers that determine the speed profiles in the path segment that precedes the way-points. In this way, the waiting time is changed in a speed variation. For example, let us consider the interval (p_j^i, p_{j+1}^i) and the waiting time w_{j+1}^i . When they are sent to the local AV i controller, it determines the forecast speed $v_{j,j+1}^i$ that the AV i must maintain in the path segment between p_j^i and p_{j+1}^i of length S^i to substitute the initial value $v^i(0)$.

A. Central Optimizer Algorithm

The CO has to detect whether some collisions can occur among the AVs on the basis of the paths determined by the AV local controllers. To this aim the CO has to simulate the system intersection and the AVs motion along the paths, and to apply an optimization algorithm. The optimization has to minimize the number of collisions and select the minimum values of the the waiting times that guarantee the Euclidean distance between the AVs greater than a safety threshold. The CO executes Algorithm 1 using an optimization tool such as the Nelder-Mead algorithm, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Genetic Algorithm (GA), or similar algorithms that are able to update the waiting times at each iteration run to minimize the objective function. The steps of Algorithm 1 are explained in the following.

In Step 1 the CO stores the data received by the local AV controllers. Moreover, the variable *safety* is set equal to a threshold representing the minimal distance imposed

Algorithm 1 CO algorithm

Step 1. Initialization $collision \leftarrow 0$ $T \leftarrow 0$ **for** $i=1$ to n **do** $[w_1^i, \dots, w_m^i] \leftarrow [0, \dots, 0]$ **end for** $safety \leftarrow threshold$ $Constraint \leftarrow 0$ or 1 $position \leftarrow [(x^1(0), y^1(0)), \dots, (x^n(0), y^n(0))]$ $speed \leftarrow [v^1(0), \dots, v^n(0)]$ **for** $i=1$ to n **do** $\mathbf{p}^i \leftarrow [p_1^i, \dots, p_m^i]$ **end for** $path \leftarrow [s^1(x), \dots, s^n(x)]$ **Step 2. Updating the waiting times through the optimization algorithm** $T = T + 1$ **for** $i=1$ to n **do** $\mathbf{w}^i \leftarrow [w_1^i, \dots, w_m^i]$ **end for****Step 3. Imposing the non-negative waiting times****if** $Constraint = 0$ **then****for** $i=1$ to n **do****for** $j=1$ to m **do****if** $w_j^i < 0$ **then** $w_j^i = 0$ **end if****end for****end for****end if****Step 4. Performing simulation**

Perform a simulation of the AVs motion at the intersection using position, speed, \mathbf{w}^i , \mathbf{p}^i and path

Step 5. AVs distance calculation

Calculate at each time instant t of the simulation the Euclidean distance among AVs:

for $i=1$ to n **do****for** $k=1$ to n with $k \neq i$ **do** $d_{ik} = \|(x^i(t), s^i(x(t))) - (x^k(t), s^k(x(t)))\|$ **if** $d_{ik} < safety$ **then** $collision = collision + 1$ **end if****end for****end for****Step 6. The CO algorithm ends or the optimization algorithm performs new waiting times based on the variable "collision"****if** $collision = 0$ OR $T = T_{max}$ **then****CO algorithm ends.****else** $collision$ is passed to the optimization algorithm;the optimization algorithm **decides** the new \mathbf{w}^i ;**go to Step 2.****end if**

between two AVs to avoid collisions. Variable *Constraint* is needed to differentiate optimization algorithms that can insert constraints, and algorithms that can only optimize the objective function. For example, if a GA is used then it is possible to apply the constraints on vectors \mathbf{w}^i . On the contrary, if the Nelder-Mead optimization algorithm is applied (as in the case of the simulations of the next section), then it is not possible to impose constraints on \mathbf{w}^i . In particular, *Constraint=0* (=1) means that the optimization algorithm can not (can) impose constraints.

In Step 2 the waiting times are updated by the optimization algorithm. At the first iteration all the waiting times are equal to zero.

Step 3 is performed only if the optimization algorithm cannot impose constraints on the waiting times. In this case, if the waiting times obtained by the optimization algorithm are negative, then they are set to zero.

In Step 4, a simulation is performed by the intersection simulator that takes in account the current position of the AVs (*position*), the AVs constant speed (*speed*), the AV paths (*path*) and the way-points (\mathbf{p}^i).

In Step 5, during the simulation, the Euclidean distance among the AVs is monitored along the paths. If a distance between two AVS is less than the parameter *safety*, then a collision is detected.

In Step 6, if $collision = 0$ then the CO algorithm ends. On the contrary, the number of collisions is sent to the optimization algorithm that determines the new waiting times to be updated in Step 2. We assume that if Algorithm 1 after a maximum number of iterations $T = T_{max}$ does not find $collision = 0$, then the Algorithm goes to an end and the CO imposes the precedence rules of the AVs without optimization.

Finally, when the CO algorithm ends with $collision = 0$, the CO transmits the waiting times to the local AV controllers that determine the speed profile in each path segment. The speed profiles are performed by the AVs to pass the intersection without collisions.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we implement the proposed method to control the intersection shown in Fig. 1.

The intersection is designed in Matlab/Simulink environment with Automated Driving toolbox that is able to control the vehicle dynamics by the waiting time specification and the determination of the spline starting from the way-points. The presented results are obtained by a personal computer equipped with an Intel Core i7-8565U CPU, 32 GB of RAM.

To simulate the system, we consider a set of $n = 4$ AVs and for each AV $i \in V$ we determine a random values of the way points \mathbf{p}^i , and the current position $(x^i(0), y^i(0))$. Moreover, the initial constant speed $v^i(0)$ is set to 30km/h for each vehicle.

Algorithm 1 is applied to minimize the waiting times by avoiding collisions using the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm that finds the first local minimum in few iterations. We set the

maximum number of iterations of Algorithm 1 to $T_{max} = 60$.

In order to show the behaviour of the proposed algorithm, Fig. 5 depicts the values of the objective function obtained by the CO algorithm (the number of collisions), at each iteration of a single simulation run. It is evident that in this case the number of collisions reaches the value zero after 9 iterations and in few seconds.

Fig. 5: Objective function value during the iteration.

Figure 6 shows the considered scenario without control: it is apparent that the AVs collide. On the contrary, the application of the control strategy with the obtained new speed profiles allows the AV to avoid the collisions as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6: AV in the intersection scenario with collision.

In order to study the performance of the proposed control strategy, a simulation campaign of 100 different scenarios

Fig. 7: AV in the intersection scenario without collision.

are performed: Fig. 8 shows the number of collisions for all the simulations.

Fig. 8: Number of collision per simulation.

More than 86 simulations obtained 0 collisions and in the remaining cases the number of collisions is lower than 3. In all the cases the results are obtained in few seconds. Hence, the results show that the algorithm can be effectively adopted for addressing AIM problems.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an Autonomous Intersection Management (AIM) with the objective of avoiding collisions among Autonomous Vehicles that have to cross an intersection without traffic lights.

The proposed Control System is managed by a Central Optimizer (CO) that collects positions, speeds and paths of the CAVs as they enter a predefined Control Zone, including the intersection. Moreover, the CO iteratively simulates the motion of vehicles along their paths and determines the waiting times for each CAV at each waypoint to guarantee no collisions. The waiting times are sent back to the CAV local controller, which determines the vehicle speed profile to cross the intersection. The simulations show the effectiveness of the proposed method that provides a solution in few iterations in a large number of cases.

Future research will apply the proposed methodology considering more complex situations involving larger number of vehicles and intersection with more than four lanes.

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